

SANOAT KORXONALARINING OQOVA SUVLARINI TOZALASHDA MAHALLIY XOMASHYOLARDAN FOYDALANISH

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Annotatsiya. Hozirgi kunda butun dunyoda juda ko'p miqdordagi maishiy, qishloq xo'jaligi va sanoat chiqindi suvlari atrof muhitga tashlanmoqda. XXI asrda toza suvning yetishmasligi va uni tozalash muammolari BMTning dunyo suv resurslari holati to'g'risidagi hisobotida "Chiqindi suv: foydalanilmagan potentsial" da ilgari surilgan. Sanoatdagi texnologik suvlarni tozalash uchun eng samarali sorbentlar ko'mir, bentonit va x.k. maxalliy xomashyodan foydalanish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar:

O'zbekistonda tabiiy sorbentlar sifatida sanoatda bentonidan keng foydalaniladi va bunga qo'shimcha ravishda tabiiy gazni tozalashda Angren qung'ir ko'miri ham sorbent vazifasini bajaradi. Kimyo sanoatida eksportbop mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish uchun tuzsizlantirilgan va kimyoviy tozalangan suvdan foydalanish lozim. Buning uchun yuqori sifatli sorbentlarni tayyorlash maqsadga muvofiqdir. Kimyo sanoati uchun Rossiya federatsiyasidan sorbentlar import qilinib kelinmoqda, kon-metallurgiya sohasiga esa Gollandiyaning Norit firmasidan maxsus sorbent ham olinmoqda. Shularning barchasini inobatga olib O'zbekiston Respublikasida ham mahalliy xomashyolar asosida sorbentlarni tayyorlash maqsadga muvofiq. Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi xududidagi ichimlik suvi va sanoat korxonalarining texnologik suvlarini tozalash uchun tabiiy sorbentlar sifatida tan olingan ko'mir va bentonitdan foydalanish mumkin.[1]

Ichimlik suvi va korxonalarining texnologik suvlarini tozalash muammosining ilmiy yechimi maxalliy xomashyolar ko'mir va bentonit aralashmalaridan tayyorlangan sorbentlar yaratish. Sanoatda texnologik va ichimlik suvlarini tozalashda eng samarali sorbentlar bentonit va ko'mir xisoblanadi. Ulardan foydalanish afzalligi xomashyoning mavjudligi va arzonligi etarli darajada yuqori ekspluatatsion xususiyatlari mavjudligi.

Ichimlik suvi va sanoat korxonalarining texnologik suvlarini tozalash uchun fizik (issiqlik bilan ishlov berish) va kimyoviy (modifikatsiya qiluvchi vositalarni tanlash) usullaridan foydalangan holda, mahalliy xomashyodan sorbentlarning yangi namunalari va tarkibi, ularning g'ovakliligi, shishish darajasi, sorbtsion qobiliyati, kationli, anionli birikmalarini ichimlik suvi va sanoat suvlaridan so'rib olish qobiliyati o'rganiladi. Bundan tashqari ishlab chiqarishda sorbentlardan bir necha bor foydalanish uchun, ularni qayta tiklash maqsadida donador sorbentlarni olishning texnologik sxemasi ishlab chiqiladi.

Respublikamizda ichimlik suvi va texnologik suvlarni tozalash uchun chetdan valyutaga import qilinib kelinayotgan sorbentlarning o'rnini bosuvchi maxalliy xomashyodan tayyorlangan arzon sorbentlardan foydalanishga extiyoj mavjud. Qoraqalpog'iston hududidagi ichimlik suvi va sanoat korxonalarining texnologik suvlarini tozalash va buning uchun zarur bo'lgan sorbentlar mahalliy xomashyolar ko'mir va bentonit aralashmalari asosida olinadi.[2]

Ichimlik suvi va sanoat korxonalarining texnologik suvlarini tozalash uchun sorbentlardan foydalanishning hozirgi holati o'rganiladi, xorijiy davlatlarning suvni tozalash uchun ishlatiladigan sorbentlar olish bo'yicha ilg'or tajribalari va yutuqlari to'liq o'rganiladi va taxlil qilinadi, sorbentlik xususiyatlarga ega bo'lgan turli xil mahalliy sorbentlar (ko'mir, bentonit va x.k.) turlari o'rganiladi va ularning sorbtsion xususiyatlarini aniqlash va oshirish uchun sinovlar o'tkaziladi, sorbentlik xususiyatlariga ega xomashyolar ko'mir va bentonitdan zamonaviy tahlil usullarini qo'llagan holda kimyoviy va minerologik tarkiblari o'rganiladi, ularning sifatiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar aniqlanadi va tahlil qilinadi, zamonaviy usulda mikroskopik taxlil amalga oshiriladi. [3].

Fizik (issiqlik bilan ishlov berish) va kimyoviy (modifikatsiya qiluvchi vositalarni tanlash) usullaridan foydalangan holda, mahalliy xomashyodan tayyorlangan yangi namunadagi sorbentlarning tarkibi, ularning g'ovakliligi, shishish darajasi, sorbtsion qobiliyati, kationli va anionli birikmalarini ichimlik suvi va sanoat suvlaridan so'rib olish qobiliyati o'rganiladi, ko'mirning dekarbonizatsiyalanish nuqtalarini va bentonitning bog'lovchilik xususiyatlari o'rganiladi, ko'mir va bentonit asosida olinadigan

sorbentlarning har-xil nisbatdagi mutanosiblik darajasi tadqiq qilinadi va natijalar asosida ko‘mir-bentonit gibridd sorbentlari yaratiladi [4].

Ko‘mir va bentonit asosida olinadigan yangi sorbentlardan bir necha marotaba qayta foydalanish imkoniyatlari o‘rganiladi va ishlab chiqarishda bir necha bor foydalanish uchun donador sorbentlarni olishning texnologik sxemasi ishlab chiqiladi, istiqbolli namunalar ishlab chiqarish sharoitida yarim sanoat sinovlaridan o‘tkaziladi va sorbentlarni olishning yaratilgan texnologik sxemasi ishlab chiqarishga joriy etish uchun tavsiya etiladi, tadqiqot natijalari asosida Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida suvni tejash va aylanma suv sifatida ishlatish maqsadida, ichimlik suvi va sanoat korxonalarining texnologik suvlarini tozalash uchun maxalliy xomashyolardan yangi sorbent ishlab chiqarish yo‘lga qo‘yiladi [5].

1-rasm. Sanoat korxonalarining texnologik suvlarini tozalash uchun mahalliy xomashyodan sorbentlar olish usullarini ishlab chiqish moslamasi

XULOSA

Yangi ishlanmani joriy qilish orqali tarmoqlarda mavjud muammolarni yechimini topish va ularni bartaraf etish mumkin. Ishlanmani nafaqat Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida balki butun Respublika bo‘ylab joriy qilish yo‘lga qo‘yiladi. Mahalliy xom ashyolardan sorbentlar ishlab chiqish va uni tijoratlashtirish natijasida import o‘rnini bosuvchi sorbent yaratiladi. Ishlab chiqiladigan sorbentlarni nafaqat suvni tozalash balki gazni tozalash uchun ham ishlatish mumkin bo‘ladi [6]. Bu esa o‘z navbatida neft-gaz sanoati uchun ham foydali bo‘ladi. Ilmiy ishlanmani joriy qilish va keng miqyosda qo‘llash uchun yetarli darajada xom ashyo bazasi mavjud.

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PROBLEMS OF WATER RESPIRATORY SYSTEMS OF NUKUS CITY AND PROSPECTS FOR THEIR DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation. This work analyzes the state of wastewater systems in the city of Nukus in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the problems of these systems and their solutions. Examples of the implementation of programs to modernize the sewerage system are given: separate sections of sewerage networks were built and re-routed in the city of Nukus; sewage pumping stations were reconstructed; a new technology was used to repair external drainage networks without opening the earthen covering. The documents reflect the condition, problems of drainage systems and plans for their improvement. Various measures for the reconstruction of existing networks and structures are presented.

Key words: *water disposal systems, reconstruction, pumping station, sewerage, sewage treatment program*

Introduction

One of the priorities of housing policy is to ensure comfortable living conditions and accessibility of utilities for the population. The state of the engineering systems of the city of Nukus is characterized by growing physical and moral wear and tear of equipment; insufficient capacity of pipelines and collectors; significant overload of right- and left-bank treatment facilities; lack of an organized storm drainage system; an increase in the volume of generated solid waste and the presence of unauthorized landfills. lands, life support systems, long-term target program, state program. Engineering systems of the city of Nukus must not only ensure the standard level of performance of all life-supporting functions, but also make it possible to implement promising projects for the development of the urban environment, construction of housing and new social facilities and business infrastructure.

Methods

Policy documents aimed at improving the wastewater system of Nukus. The goal of government programs is to improve the quality of provided housing and communal services, modernize and develop housing and communal services, increase the level of reliability, quality and efficiency of the public utilities complex. The objectives of most programs include the development and modernization of water supply, water disposal and wastewater treatment facilities, increasing the reliability of life support engineering systems, and developing the main directions, principles and targets for the development of the city of Nukus.

In 2022, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted on the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026.

Within the framework of the Development Strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, including “Goal 34: Development of the system of engineering, communication and social infrastructure of the regions, as well as the service sector,” the creation of technically and technologically modernized local and individual wastewater treatment facilities is especially important, which will ensure the reuse of treated water and reduce excess costs, including for the treatment of wastewater generated in areas without a sewer system. [1,11].